

Autonomous Weapons a Military Ethical Question

Artur Victoria

Today's autonomous weapon systems have independent modes and therefore only operate autonomously for short periods.

They are also limited in the tasks in which they are used, the types of targets they attack and the circumstances in which they are used. The development of the Brimstone air-to-ground missile is a good illustration of how autonomous weapons evolve.

Brimstone was originally designed as a "throw and forget" weapon against armoured vehicle formations using millimetre-wave active radar to ensure accuracy against moving targets.

Experience in Afghanistan has led to the addition of laser guidance, thus allowing the operator to distinguish between targets in order to reduce the possibility of civilian casualties.

Brimstone can be programmed by the operator to suit specific mission requirements and thus gives the weapon the ability to distinguish between targets and self-destruct if it cannot find a target in the designated area.

Brimstone has an autonomous targeting capability as it is released from the aircraft and has the ability to determine where on a target the best impact causing the most damage.

The Brimstone air-to-ground missile was used extensively during Operation Ellamy over Libya in 2011 and currently by the Royal Air Force over Iraq. In all the more than 120 missiles that was fired on Libya with a success rate of 98%.

The missile was tested on an MQ-9 Reaper, the first time a standalone weapon was fired from a remotely guided platform.

In April 2015, Naval Research in Arlington announced that it has tested its LOCUST UAV Swarming Technology program. The LOCUST program includes a tube-based launcher that can launch low-cost UAVs in rapid succession.

This innovative technology utilizes information sharing among UAVs, enabling autonomous collaborative behaviour on defensive or offensive missions. Demonstrations took place at various locations and 9 UAVs worked fully autonomously in synchronized flight.

The LOCUST program uses Coyote pumps made by BAE Systems that are electronically powered. The UAV has a cruising speed of 60 knots and a top speed of 85 knots and

can operate at altitudes up to 20,000 feet. The Navy is planning a ship-based demonstration using up to 30 UAVs.

There is now a wide range of missile defense systems that can be described as operating autonomously.

- The Phalanx weapon system near the weapon system is in active service with 25 navies and was first deployed in 1980.

- The Aegis combat system was introduced in 1983 and Patriot in 2002.

In addition to these, there are various active vehicle protection systems in operation or under development. Such systems are designed to detect and intercept missiles, rockets (RPGs) or artillery blasts before reaching the target. Such systems are beyond human control given the extremely short response times required to counteract the threat.

The SHARK Active Protection System developed by Thales and IBD Deisenroth Engineering is a good example of such systems. A combination of radar and optronic sensors detect threats at very short intervals and destroy by releasing a pyrotechnic charge. The incoming gust disintegrates and the remaining energy is absorbed by the vehicle's armour.

Similar systems were developed by KBP Instrument in Russia, Artis, and Raytheon in the United States and Rafael in Israel.

There is no internationally agreed definition of an autonomous weapon that gives rise to a debate on this issue.

From the point of view of common sense, it makes sense to define an autonomous weapon as one that selects and involves targets on its own, and a semi-autonomous weapon such as one in which a human being is selecting specific targets for firing.

Given this definition, it becomes clear that there are currently only a few truly autonomous systems in operation.

It is also becoming apparent that the above common-sense definition is not sufficient to define exactly where the line is between autonomous and semi-autonomous weapon systems.

Another definition can be introduced between autonomous and semi-autonomous systems, an autonomous system supervised by humans.

Thus, the Brimstone missile described above would fall into this category because the operator would decide whether to engage a specific target or not.

In the case of an autonomous system, however, the operator makes the decision to launch a weapon to search for and destroy a general target class in a wide area but is not making a decision on which specific objectives to pursue.

The LOCUST project seems to correspond to the definition of a truly autonomous system.

Rapid technological advances and changing threats mean that capabilities that seem impossible today.

Rapid technological advances and changing threats mean that capabilities that seem impossible today will come to fruition much sooner than we realize. Remotely controlled vehicles on the ground in the air or on water will soon be replaced by increasingly autonomous operating systems.

The Franco-German plan to develop a "new" MALE-UAV for operational use in about 10 years is a step in the wrong direction, unless such a system can perform the intended operations autonomously.

The current political view, at least in Germany, is, however, to prohibit autonomy in future weapons without any clear evidence that such systems are harmful.

In fact, human-supervised autonomous systems such as Brimstone have reduced civilian casualties in a war scenario. In the heat of battle, technical indicators are sometimes more reliable than human judgment. In 1988, for example, the USS Vincennes shot down an Iranian aircraft because the crew believed the aircraft was descending to attack. In fact, the onboard computers accurately indicated that it was rising to get away. In the case of the USS Vincennes, human operators overtook the Aegis automatic system and created a humane and diplomatic disaster.

The autonomous system uses Artificial Intelligence - AI -

The use in data processing for intelligence reporting has been observed by (HAMILTON AND KREUZER, 2018). According to Hasik (2018), Americans' third offset strategy is based on a new institutional organization and new technologies related to autonomous systems and AI.

Recent projects include the US Air Force's Strategic Capabilities Office (SCO) Perdix drone swarm and the US Navy Sea Hunter project, a standalone anti-submarine vessel, and even the secret Ghost Fleet project.

In organizational terms, we highlight the Defense Innovation Unit Experimentation (DIUx) as well as the Algorithmic Warfare Cross-Functional Team, which analyzes large amounts of video collected by drones.

Projects such as:

the Future Combat System, a set of fourteen systems interconnected by an extensive robust electronic attack communication network that would allow commanders to have a real-time view of the battlefield with immediate decisions, together with the interconnection system.

Multiple warheads that autonomously decide route changes and targets when another missile simultaneously launched is destroyed.

The Maven project, also known as Algorithmic Warfare Cross functional Team, aims to bring to the military various technologies already developed in civilian data collection and processing in order to raise new capabilities for the artificial intelligence industry.

Thus there is a redefinition of Autonomous Systems, - Systems that can change their behaviour in response to unanticipated events during their operation.

That is, they are systems that, when interacting with their domain, are able to learn and make decisions without external agents dictating the command or having little influence.

Unmanned Underwater Vehicle (UUVs), such as those described by NAVSEA PMS-403, and Unmanned Air Vehicle (UAVs), such as the Predator and Global Hawk built by the Americans, are some examples.

Stationary autonomous weapon systems already exist for the purpose of defense, especially from air threats. However, the autonomy to offensively select and engage human targets. The US Army wants to develop small drones to automatically identify and target vehicles and people.

This may allow faster response to threats, but it can also be a step toward standalone drones that attack targets without human supervision.

The balance of power on the battlefield may be affected by the use of AI - especially by enabling small but deep technological development, they can use these systems to increase their power influence.

The asymmetric use of these capabilities may also be able to destabilize countries that do not have the necessary countermeasures. Another point to be emphasized is the potential for the modernization of equipment already outdated without the need to follow all the stages of its technological development, that is, taking a leap of intermediate steps.

Currently the US researches to apply AI in electronic warfare (Electronic Warfare - EW); intelligence,

monitoring and reconnaissance (intelligence, surveillance and reconnaissance - ISR); reconnaissance, surveillance and target acquisition (RSTA); offensive cyber operations

(OCO); signals intelligence (SIGINT); processing, exploitation and dissemination (PED); and big data analytics.

Also as an example are systems used by the US Navy that can automatically select the target, making the attack decision without human intervention such as Phalanx CIWS, which automatically fires at supersonic enemy aircraft and missiles.

Thus in the concept of autonomous weapons can be subdivided an autonomous system, able to select their targets by their own decision, and fire-and-forget system, once selected the target.

References:

ALLEN, G. C. Understanding China's AI Strategy: Clues to Chinese Strategic Thinking on Artificial Intelligence and National Security. Center for a New American Security (CNAS), Washington DC, United States, 2019.

ALLEN, J.; HUSAIN, A. AI will change the balance of power. U.S. Naval Institute Proceedings, v. 144, n. 8, p. 26 – 31, 2018. ISSN 0041798X.

BARANIUK, C. World war r. New Scientist, v. 224, n. 2995, p. 38 – 41, 2014. ISSN 02624079.

BERGHEL, H. Malice domestic: The Cambridge analytica dystopia. Computer, v. 51, n.5, p. 84–89, May 2018. ISSN 0018-9162.

CHANSORIA, M. To ban or regulate autonomous weapons: An Indian response. Bulletin of the Atomic Scientists, v. 72, n. 2, p. 120–121, 2016. ISSN 19383282.

CHINA. New Generation Artificial Intelligence Development Plan. Ministry of Industry and Information Technology, Science and Technology Department, Beijing, China, 2017. Disponível em: <www.miit.gov.cn/n1146290/n4388791/c5960863/content.html>.

CHINA. China AI Development Report 2018. China Institute for Science and Technology Policy, Tsinghua University, Haidian, Beijing, China, 2018.

CRONK, T. M. DOD Unveils Its Artificial Intelligence Strategy. U.S. DEPARTMENT OF DEFENSE, 2019.

DAFOE, A. Global politics and the governance of artificial intelligence. Journal of International Affairs, v. 72, n. 1, p. 121 – 126, 2018. ISSN 0022197X.

DARPA. Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI). Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency, Arlington, VA, USA, 2016.

DOD. SUMMARY OF THE 2018 DEPARTMENT OF DEFENSE ARTIFICIAL

INTELLIGENCE STRATEGY: Harnessing AI to Advance Our Security and Prosperity.

GIANNETTI, W. Artificial intelligence: Myths and realities. Air & Space Power Journal,

v. 32, n. 3, p. 92 – 95, 2018. ISSN 1555385X.

GUERSENZVAIG, A. Autonomous weapon systems: Failing the principle of discrimination. IEEE Technology and Society Magazine, v. 37, n. 1, p. 55 – 61, 2018. ISSN 0278-0097.

HAMBLING, D. Us is seeking smart killer drones. *NEW SCIENTIST*, v. 237, n. 3171, p.8, 2018. ISSN 02624079.

HAMILTON, S. P.; KREUZER, M. P. The big data imperative: Air force intelligence for the information age. *Air & Space Power Journal*, v. 32, n. 1, p. 4 – 20, 2018. ISSN 1555385X.

HASIK, J. Beyond the third offset: Matching plans for innovation to a theory of victory. *JFQ: Joint Force Quarterly*, n. 91, p. 14 – 21, 2018. ISSN 10700692.

HENNIG, J.; SCHWARTZ, P.; BAILEY, K. Mission command on semi-automatic. *Army AL&T Magazine*, p. 50 – 55, 2017. ISSN 15298507.

KELLER, J. Army wants artificial intelligence technology for cyber and electronic warfare. *Military & Aerospace Electronics*, v. 29, n. 6, p. 6 – 7, 2018. ISSN 10469079b.

KELLER, J. DARPA eyes tiny insects as models for artificial intelligence (ai) computing. *Military & Aerospace Electronics*, v. 30, n. 2, p. 28, 2019. ISSN 10469079a.

KELLER, J. IARPA seeks to apply trusted computing to artificial intelligence and machine learning models. *Military & Aerospace Electronics*, v. 30, n. 1, p. 8 – 9, 2019. ISSN 10469079b.

LEWIS, L. Insights for the Third Offset: Addressing Challenges of Autonomy and Artificial Intelligence in Military Operations. Center for Naval Analyses, Arlington, United States, 2017.

MAAS, M. M. How viable is international arms control for military artificial intelligence? three lessons from nuclear weapons. *Contemporary Security Policy*, Routledge, v. 0, n. 0, p. 1–27, 2019.

MAGNUSON, S. DoD making push to catch up on artificial intelligence. *National Defense*, p. 22 – 23, 2017. ISSN 00921491.

MELANIE, R. Us DOD releases first artificial intelligence strategy. *Jane's Defence Weekly*, n. 11, 2019.

MEUSER, C. Franken weapons loom on the horizon. *U.S. Naval Institute Proceedings*, v. 142, n. 7, p. 28 – 33, 2016. ISSN 0041798X.